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[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10680045](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10680045)

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Recommended Citation

Gueldich, H. (2023). The prohibition of slavery and human trafficking as peremptory norms. *American Yearbook of International Law*, vol. 2, n. 1, 168-234, Article 5

Available at:

<https://ayil.rf.gd/index.php/home/issue/current>

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The prohibition of slavery and human trafficking as peremptory norms

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Introduction

Jus cogens is in vogue.

“While not so very long ago, peremptory international law was regarded by international lawyers as an idea of little more than academic interest, today it is part of the common rhetoric of the international legal profession. More than ever before international lawyers resort to jus cogens for the construction and reinforcement of legal arguments” (Ulf, 2011).

In fact, peremptory norms as a concept have been significantly influenced and raised in International law through the contributions of Professor Verdross (Verdross, 1937; Verdross, 1966)¹. His contributions influenced the work of the International Law Commission on the Law of Treaties through

¹ Professor Verdross derived them from natural law. He believed that there are rules that have the jus cogens nature in International law as the general principles of morality or the common public policy of legal systems in civilized nations constitutes a restriction on the obligations of the contractual states. He considered that these rules nullified treaties of immoral purpose. After three decades, Verdross also emphasized that there are rules in International law that have the jus cogens nature to satisfy the higher interest of the international community as a whole and these rules are absolute. Hence, he referred to some examples of jus cogens rules such as the prohibition of the use of force and all rules of general international law that have a humanitarian purpose.

adopting this notion in article 53 of the Vienna Convention. Therefore, the notion of “peremptory norms” became part of positive International law through both articles 53² and 64³ of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969.

The legal consequences of the existence of peremptory norms are the following:

“Peremptory norms do not accept any exception even if it is unanimous; any reservations to provisions relating to peremptory norms are inadmissible and any unilateral act leading to breach or violation of a peremptory norm may not be taken” (Stefan Kadelbach, 2006).

Furthermore, we can confirm that:

“Peremptory norms or jus cogens hold a unique position in International law. Unlike customary international law and treaty law, they abide to no derivation and all states are bound regardless of their willingness to be bound” (Handayani, 2019).

In essence,

“the concept of peremptory norms (jus cogens) expanded to most branches of International law and became a necessary and so essential concept in the life of the international community and the consolidation of the status of International law. The main function of these norms is to maintain the international peace and security, to protect people and individuals and to promote the fundamental values of the international community as a whole. According to the importance of these norms to the international community, there are a set of jus cogens rules accepted and recognized by it. These norms are the prohibition of the use of force, genocide, slavery, racial discrimination, torture and the right of self-determination” (Menshaw, 2019).

²Article 53 stipulates that: “A treaty is void if, at the time of its conclusion, it conflicts with a peremptory norm of general international law. For the purposes of the present Convention, a peremptory norm of general international law is a norm accepted and recognized by the international community of states as a Unilateral acts and peremptory norms whole as a norm from which no derogation is permitted and which can be modified only by a subsequent norm of general international law of the same nature”.

³Article 64 stipulates that: “If a new peremptory norm of general international law emerges, any existing treaty which is in conflict with that norm becomes void and terminates”.

In other words, we are dealing with the hard core of human rights which are

“the imperative human rights to which it is not permissible to derogate under any circumstances, not even in a state of crisis or threat of war, exceptional public danger, proclamation of a state of exception, etc.” (Salmon, 2001).

This is to recall the definition of the Conclusion 2 of Chapter V of the International Law Commission's Report on “Peremptory norm of general international law (*jus cogens*)”⁴ as following:

“A peremptory norm of general international law (*jus cogens*) is a norm accepted and recognised by the international community of states as a whole as a norm from which no derogation is permitted and which can be modified only by a subsequent norm of general international law (*jus cogens*) having the same character”⁵.

This hard core of human rights is composed of at least four rights that cannot be excluded under any pretext: the right to life, the prohibition of torture and inhuman or degrading treatment, the prohibition of slavery and the non-retroactivity of the criminal law and the legality of the offences and penalties. These four rights are the common part of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights of 1950, the Inter-American Convention on Human Rights of 1969 and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966.

Moreover, the rights contained in this hard core are intangible,

⁴At its sixty-seventh session (2015), the International Law Commission decided to include the topic “*Jus cogens*” in its program of work and appointed Mr. Dire Tladi as Special Rapporteur for the topic. At its 3504th meeting, on 7 August 2019, the International Law Commission expressed its deep appreciation for the outstanding contribution of the Special Rapporteur, Mr. Dire Tladi, which had enabled the Commission to bring to a successful conclusion its first reading of the draft conclusions on peremptory norms of general international law (*jus cogens*), A/74/10, paragraphs 46, page 141 and 55, page 142.

⁵A/74/10, conclusion 2, page 142.

which means that they are inviolable and sacred. This does not mean that the list is exhaustive. But in general, all human rights are bearers of the idea of dignity. However, the rights of the hard core are seen as the ultimate threshold of this dignity. It is a sort of recognition that the moral aspect of International law as the peremptory norms represent the rules of International public order. Additionally, the intangibility of certain rights entails absolute obligations for states. On the one hand, states may not infringe on affirmed rights. On the other hand, the state must protect individuals so that their rights are not violated.

In other words, it is a sort of recognition of the primacy and supremacy of these peremptory norms from any other rule of International law, reflecting the existence of a kind of hierarchy between the rules of international law.

The right to life is the primary condition for the existence of man and his physical continuity. That is why this right overrides all other human rights. Thus, in the strict sense, the right to life protects the human being from the damage to the bodily integrity of another person. Therefore, it is primarily the prohibition of murder. However, generally, the right to life is an expression designating the set of rights that are attributed to living beings in general, and to human beings in particular.

Among the non exhaustive list attached to the conclusion of the Report on the Peremptory norms of general International Law,

the “Prohibition of Slavery” was mentioned.

“Without prejudice to the existence or subsequent emergence of other peremptory norms of general International law (jus cogens), a non-exhaustive list of norms that the International Law Commission has previously referred to as having that status is to be found in the annex to the present draft conclusions”,

there is “(f) The prohibition of slavery”⁶.

“(10) The annex also includes the prohibition of slavery as the sixth norm on the list of peremptory norms of general international law (jus cogens) previously referred to by the Commission. The prohibition of slavery was referred to by the Commission as a peremptory norm of general international law (jus cogens) in the commentary to draft article 26 of the articles on responsibility of states for internationally wrongful acts. The commentary to draft article 40 of the articles on responsibility of states for internationally wrongful acts refers to the prohibition of slavery and slave trade. The commentary to the draft articles on the law of treaties, on its part, refers to the prohibition of the trade in slaves”⁷.

“(14) The norms in the annex are presented in no particular order. Their order does not, in any way, signify a hierarchy among them”⁸.

In this context, we can ask the following question: Why is the prohibition slavery among the peremptory norms of general international law?

Everyone is aware that every year, all over the world, hundreds of thousands of women, children and men are trafficked into conditions amounting to slavery. One major problem of human trafficking is that it constitutes a gross violation of human rights (Elom Ngwe, Oko Elechi, 2012)⁹.

6A/74/10, conclusion 23, page 146.

7A/74/10, conclusion 23, Commentary paragraph 10, page 206.

8A/74/10, conclusion 23, Commentary paragraph 14, page 207.

9“Some of the victims of human trafficking are used for sexual exploitation, domestic labour, forced labour or debt bondage, hence many view trafficking in persons as another form of modern day slavery. Most victims of human trafficking are recruited from the developing countries. It is widespread in countries undergoing civil war, or afflicted by political or economic instability. The popular destinations of most victims of human trafficking are the rich countries of Western Europe and North

According to the facts and figures of the International Labour Organisation (ILO) in 2016,

“an estimated 40.3 million people are in modern slavery, including 24.9 million in forced labour and 15.4 million in forced marriage. It means there are 5.4 victims of modern slavery for every 1,000 people in the world. 1 in 4 victims of modern slavery are children. Out of the 24.9 million people trapped in forced labour, 16 million people are exploited in the private sector such as domestic work, construction or agriculture; 4.8 million people in forced sexual exploitation, and 4 million persons in forced labour imposed by state authorities (...)¹⁰.”

Due to the complex nature and secrecy of this type of crime, it is very difficult to know exactly how many people have been subjected to trafficking in the world.

Moreover, slavery and human trafficking is a very sensitive topic. There are no reliable statistics on the extent of human trafficking anywhere in the world.

“One reason for the lack of reliable data on human trafficking is because this is a crime that is hidden-as it is part of the underground economy” (Ngwe, Oko Elechi, 2012).

Indeed, human trafficking today is a global business and the source of lucrative profits for the traffickers.

According to the International Labour Organisation (ILO), the total illicit profit produced in one year by trafficked labourers is estimated to be about US\$32 billion¹¹. Furthermore, there are millions of people victims of forced labour all over the World. “Over 21 million people are victims of forced labour and 4.5 million of these are victims of forced sexual exploitation according to the ILO. The 2014

America. Asia is both a destination and the origin of victims of human trafficking (...).”

¹⁰ILO Forced Labour, Human Trafficking and Slavery, <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/forced-labour/lang--en/index.htm>

¹¹ILO, Profits and poverty: The Economics of forced Labour, https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---ed_norm/---declaration/documents/publication/wcms_243391.pdf

Global Slavery Index of the Walk Free Foundation on the other estimates that 35.8 million people are currently held in modern slavery (...)" (Tseliso, 2015).

Transnational crime is perceived as a major threat to global peace and security and one that is capable of undermining the economic, social, political and cultural development of the international community¹². Among transnational crimes, there is slavery, which consists in the appropriation of one person by another and which leads to the negation of the legal personality of the appropriate person. In addition, human trafficking is an affront to human dignity, which often involves psychological terror and physical violence. Trafficking encompasses issues of human rights and rule of law enforcement and crime control of inequality and discrimination, of corruption, economic deprivation and migration.

As a matter of fact,

"Human trafficking first came to the attention of the International community in the late 1980's. By the beginning of the 21st century, it had been recognised as a serious global problem that needed global responses. The United Nations responded in 2000 with the publication of the UN Convention against Transnational Organised Crime and its Supplementary Protocols. The Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children (the Palermo Protocol) set out the first definition of human trafficking that is still the benchmark for defining human trafficking

¹²In this regard, Kofi Annan announced: "(...) no nation can defend itself against these threats entirely on its own. Dealing with today's challenges – from ensuring that deadly weapons do not fall into dangerous hands to combating global climate change, from preventing the trafficking of sex slaves by organised criminal gangs to holding war criminals to account before competent courts – requires broad, deep, and sustained global cooperation. States working together can achieve things that are beyond what even the most powerful state can accomplish by itself (...)", (ANNAN, 2005, p.2).

today”¹³.

The ancient slavery, which is known as the transatlantic slave trade, in which Africans were captured, chained and transported to the United States and Latin America to work as slaves, was officially abolished around 1807 (Sowell, 2005).

“Unfortunately, human trafficking appears to have replaced this abhorrent activity as the modern day slavery of the 21st century (...)” (Elom Ngwe, Oko Elech, 2012).

The abolitionists’ publications have for long denounced that practice. It is the example of the work of the Society for Effecting the Abolition of Slave Trade (Society for the Abolition of Slave Trade) with Thomas Clarkson¹⁴ in 1787 as one of its co-founders. A replica of this Association, the Society of Friends of Black People, was born in France in 1788¹⁵. Victor Schoelcher (Schoelcher, 1842) and Randall Robinson are worthy to be mentioned in this regard (Robinson, 2001).

A review of the human trafficking literature shows that everybody is at risk of being trafficked, including men, women and children. Moreover,

“citizens of both developed and developing countries, whether educated or un-educated, are at risk of being trafficked. However, it is pertinent to point out that the poorer countries of the world are major sources of victims of

¹³Human trafficking is a modern day form of slavery, Report on Counter-Trafficking, IOM, https://ec.europa.eu/anti-trafficking/sites/antitrafficking/files/train_the_trainers_manual_1.pdf

¹⁴Great English abolitionist, he conducted investigations in the great English black port of Liverpool in 1787.

¹⁵A year later in February 1788, the Society of Friends of Black People was born in France. The Society was an association the objective of which was identical: equality of Whites and free people of colour in the colonies and immediate abolition of black slave trade and slavery.

human trafficking while the rich countries are most often the destinations of human trafficking victims” (Wlom Ngwe, Oko Elech, 2012).

Nowadays, in doctrine and in practice, we speak about “modern slavery” and “modern forms of slavery” (Bales, Cornell, 2008)¹⁶. According to an author,

“Slavery is a problem the public thinks we solved long ago, but, in fact, it’s alive and well. It has simply taken on a new form” (Gilmore, 2004)¹⁷.

Another author affirms that:

“The abolition of slavery belongs to the triumphs of history. It is an integral component of the path to human rights, democracy, and a free society. Moreover, it belongs to history. That is, however, a huge mistake. This is due to the fact that today there are more slaves now than in any other prior century. And most of them have been treated and moved around like goods on the global market” (Schirmacher, 2013).

In this regard, during the past three years, more precisely in November 2017¹⁸, it was shocking to see CNN publishing an exclusive report exposing how migrants are being sold by smugglers in Lybia. This was slavery in the classic sense of the term, and the victims were Africans coming from sub-Saharan Africa. The latter were sold as slaves, \$400 each¹⁹. In addition to alerting the Libyan authorities, CNN handed over footage as

¹⁶Modern day slavery differs remarkably from ancient slavery in several ways according to Bales and Cornell (2008). One way contemporary slavery differs from ancient slavery is that it costs much less to acquire slaves today. Some slaves, according to the authors, can be purchased for as little as ten US dollars. Secondly, slaves today are not owned for life like in the past. Slaves are owned for a limited duration, some lasting for a few years or even months. However, this puts the slave in a more precarious situation because the slave owner has no incentive to look after the slave and prolong his or her life and wellbeing to keep him or her productive for a longer period of time.

¹⁷According to Laurel Fletcher, a researcher at the Human Rights Centre and professor at UC Berkeley's law school, cited in Gilmore.

¹⁸CNN, <https://edition.cnn.com/specials/africa/libya-slave-auctions>

¹⁹CNN, <https://edition.cnn.com/2017/11/14/africa/libya-migrant-auctions/index.html>

evidence to the International Criminal Court.

A few years earlier, the World was shocked to see Yazidi women, in Iraq, led as slaves to be sold to Daesh warriors, in order to meet their sexual needs. A drama that shook the whole World. Daesh considers the Yazidi women and girls they captured to be spoils of war and systemically forces them into slavery. An article in Daesh's Dabiq Magazine entitled "The Revival of Slavery Before the Hour"²⁰ acknowledges it was reviving enslavement practices under Sharia law. Furthermore, in a document entitled, "Question and Answers on Taking and Capturing Slaves" published by Daesh's Research and Fatwa Department, Daesh grants members permission

"to buy, sell, or give female captives out as gifts and slaves, for they are merely property, which can be disposed of"²¹.

Under these practices,

"one fifth of captured Yazidi women and girls are sent to Daesh leadership as khums, a tax on war spoils, and those remaining are divided among Daesh fighters in accordance with Sharia"²².

Besides, some African and Arabic countries still practice slavery until now. Slavery in the Sahel States of Mauritania, Mali, Niger, Chad and Sudan, in particular, continues a centuries-old

²⁰"The Revival of Slavery Before the Hour", in Dabiq Magazine 14-17.

²¹Middle E. Media Res. Inst., Islamic State (ISIS) Releases Pamphlet on Female Slaves (Dec. 4, 2014), <http://www.memrijttm.org/islamic-stateisis-releases-pamphlet-on-female-slaves.html>; *Human Rights Watch*, Iraq: ISIS Escapees Describe Systematic Rape (Apr. 14, 2015), <https://www.hrw.org/news/2015/04/14/iraq-isis-escapees-describe-systematic-rape>

²²"Daesh's Gender-Based Crimes against Yazidi Women and Girls Include Genocide", Report, Global Justice Center: Human Rights Through Rule of Law, www.globaljusticecenter.net

pattern of hereditary servitude (Hall, 2011). Other forms of traditional slavery exist in parts of Ghana, Benin, Togo and Nigeria. There are other non-traditional forms of slavery in Africa today, mostly involving human trafficking and the enslavement of child soldiers and child labourers (Hall, 2011).

Such 21st century practices are completely illegal, unlawful and illegitimate. They are contrary to all international conventions and customs, but they unfortunately still took place and their authors remain unpunished.

One then wonders whether the legal framework governing the prohibition of slavery and human trafficking is completely ineffective and outdated?

In this context, we have to analyse the legal nature of the prohibition of slavery and human trafficking as peremptory norms of general international law (*jus cogens*) and delimit its consequences on the regime of criminal responsibility of individuals who had committed these crimes.

The study of the legal framework of the slavery and human trafficking's prohibition, in addition to the presentation of the different institutions aiming to protect the victims of these odious crimes, can give us an idea about the importance of a multilateral and multidisciplinary action against this scourge, especially through prevention, protection and prosecution. In this regard, we will present the different relevant legal

instruments that prohibit slavery and human trafficking.

The chapter begins by exploring the most important treaties in the contemporary world, related to the prohibition of slavery, human trafficking, Forced labour, other forms of modern slavery and other similar practices, both at the universal and regional levels. It then, identifies key elements of the offence of slavery and human trafficking.

While human trafficking and slavery or exploitation are not necessarily synonymous, it has been recognised that it can be dealt with under these provisions relating to slavery/forced labour under certain circumstances, and thus various obligations established by these human rights treaties will be relevant to this crime.

The chapter continues with an examination of state responsibility, with particular reference to the core obligations of prohibition, protection and prevention.

On the other hand, we will present the different actions and institutions within the United Nations and NGO's that are aiming to prevent and to protect the victims of such crimes all over the World.

This study is also a demonstration that the prohibition of slavery and human trafficking belongs to the peremptory norms or Jus cogens that are

“accepted and recognised by the international community of states as a whole as a norm from which no derogation is permitted and which can be modified

only by a subsequent norm of general international law having the same character”²³, following the conclusions of the study of Prof. Dire Tladi on Chapter V “Peremptory norms of General International law (Jus cogens)”.

The main conclusion is that there will be many opportunities for the regional and universal Courts to enhance individual and collective responses to slavery and human trafficking through articulation of state responsibility.

The legal framework: multiple international legal instruments prohibiting slavery and human trafficking

Many international legal instruments were signed and went operational in order to fight against slavery, servitude, forced or compulsory labour and human trafficking. The prohibition of slavery, servitude, forced labour and similar practices has been clearly established by these different instruments, demonstrating that these practices are of jus cogens nature. This international legal framework is not only taken at the Universal level (1), but also at the Regional level (2) (Haveb, 2000)²⁴.

1. The International framework at the Universal level:

The international framework at the universal level had been

²³A/74/10, conclusion 2, page 142.

²⁴It is important to recall that Tunisia is known for being the first Muslim country to abolish Slavery during the modern period (even before the United States of America), specifically, on 23 January 1846 by Ahmed I Bey. Under the French protectorate, the prohibition of Slavery dates from the Decree of 28 May 1890, which states that: “Slavery is forbidden in the Tunisian regency”.

evaluating, since the first half of the 20th century, and many texts had prohibited slavery, servitude, forced or compulsory labour, human trafficking and many other analogue practices.

1.1.Prohibition of Slavery:

Slavery is

“any system in which principles of property law are applied to people, allowing individuals to own, buy and sell other individuals, as a de jure form of property” (Brace, 2004).

The first Convention in this regard is the Convention on Slavery of 25 September 1926. This convention prohibits

“any act of capture or acquisition of an individual for the purpose of making him a slave, any act of acquisition of a slave for the purpose of selling or exchanging him, any act of transfer by way of sale or exchange of a slave acquired for the purpose of being sold or exchanged, and, in general, any act of trade or transport of slaves”.

On 25 September 1926, the League of Nations expressed a total rejection by developing this Convention on Slavery. Its provisions covered multiple forms of slavery, human trafficking and forced labour (Fischer, 1957).

In addition to that, the Universal Declaration on Human Rights of 1948 states, in article 4, that:

“no one should be held in slavery or servitude, slavery in all of its forms should be eliminated”.

1.2.Prohibition of Forced labour:

Forced labour means any work or service required of a person under threat of any punishment for which the person has not consented. The Forced Labour Convention of 28 June 1930, adopted by the International Labour Organisation (ILO), required states to abolish forced or compulsory labour in all its

forms.

When imposed by governments, forced labour does not include military conscription or penal labour. Forced labour can, similarly, be used simply to cut production costs by private and public industries or can be a form of involuntary servitude in the private sector. This type of slavery is the equivalent of contract slavery, where

“contracts are offered which guarantee employment, perhaps in a workshop or factory, but when the workers are taken to their place of employment they discover that they have instead been taken into slavery (...). It is a way of making slavery seem legitimate and necessary” (Bales, 2000).

Forced labour is only one component of human trafficking.

1.3.Prohibition of Servitude:

On the other hand, servitude is a practice, which consists in the obligation to provide a certain number of services to others, in exchange for living on the property of these persons and the impossibility of changing their living conditions. It is, in fact, a form of slavery or the state of being under the control of someone else and of having no freedom.

A specific convention has been provided for it. It is the Convention on the Abolition of Slavery, Slave Trade, and similar institutions and Practices of 30 April 1956 and which became effective on 30 April 1957. This convention prohibits any form of servitude to the human person (such as the practices by which a woman is promised or given in marriage against her will by way of cash or in-kind consideration, the transfer of the

woman and her inheritance, the transfer of a child to third parties for payment or not, to exploit it, etc.). The Convention of 1956 is better drafted than the Convention of 1926. Its articles contain more details on the constitutive elements of the crime of Slavery and Slave trade.

In particular, article 8 of the Covenant of Civil and Political Rights of 1966 (which became effective on 23 March 1976) clearly states that:

“No one shall be held in slavery, slavery and the slave all their forms shall be prohibited. No one shall be held in servitude. No one shall be required to perform force or compulsory labour”.

However, some practices are not considered forced or compulsory labour, according to Article 8 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, such as:

“1- The execution of a sentence of forced labour imposed by a court of competent jurisdiction; 2- Any military service; 3- Any national service required by law; 4- Any service required in the event of force majeure or disaster”.

1.4.Prohibition of any other similar practices:

With respect to the notion of “any other similar practices”, it seeks to prohibit trafficking in human beings or the exploitation of the prostitution of others, as required by the Convention for the Suppression of Trafficking in Human Beings or the Exploitation of the Prostitution of Others of 2 December 1949.

This convention commits states to punish any person who, in order to satisfy the passions of others, hires, involves or diverts, for the purpose of prostitution, another person, even if the latter

is consenting, or exploits the prostitution of a person, even with his or her consent.

Similarly, article 3 of the Additional Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, especially Women and Children (also referred to as the Trafficking Protocol or the Palermo Protocol), an international agreement under the UN Convention against Transnational Organised Crime (CTOC) of December 2000, which became effective on 25 December 2003, aims to prevent, suppress and punish trafficking in persons, in particular women and children.

In order to achieve these objectives, these instruments impose a variety of obligations designed to enhance national and international actions against human trafficking.

1.5. Prohibition of Human trafficking:

One outstanding feature of the Trafficking Protocol is that it not only applies to prostitution and sexual exploitation, but also to other forms of exploitation, thereby expanding its scope of application.

“This is important as the international community has recognised that victims are trafficked and exploited in non-sex sectors” (Obokata, 2019).

The Trafficking Protocol is the first global, legally binding instrument on trafficking in over half a century, and the only one with an agreed-upon definition of trafficking in persons. One of its purposes is to facilitate international cooperation in investigating and prosecuting such trafficking. Another is to

protect and assist victims of human trafficking with full respect for their rights as established in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

To be more precise, the Trafficking Protocol or the Palermo Protocol of 2003 defines human trafficking as:

“(a) (...) the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons, by means of threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power or of a position of vulnerability or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation. Exploitation shall include, at a minimum, the exploitation or the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labour or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude or the removal, manipulation or implantation of organs;

(b)The consent of a victim of trafficking in persons to the intended exploitation set forth in sub-paragraph (a) of this article shall be irrelevant where any of the means set forth in subparagraph (a) have been used;

(c)The recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of a child for the purpose of exploitation shall be considered “trafficking in persons” even if this does not involve any of the means set forth in sub-paragraph (a) of this article;

(d)“Child” shall mean any person under eighteen years of age”.

According to this text, human trafficking is the trade of humans for the purpose of forced labour, sexual slavery, or commercial sexual exploitation for the trafficker or others. This may encompass providing a spouse in the context of forced marriage, or the extraction of organs or tissues, including surrogacy and ova removal.

Human trafficking can occur within a country or trans-nationally (Shelley, 2010). Consequently,

“it is a crime against the person because of the violation of the victim's rights

of movement through coercion and because of their commercial exploitation”²⁵.

Human trafficking is the trade in people, especially women and children, and “does not necessarily involve the movement of the person from one place to another”²⁶.

Human trafficking is condemned as a violation of human rights by international conventions, namely the following texts:

1. Convention on the Abolition of Slavery, Slave Trade, and similar institutions and Practices of 30 April 1956 and which became effective on 30 April 1957;
2. Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, especially Women and Children of December 2000, which became effective on 25 December 2003;
3. Protocol against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea and Air supplementing the Convention against Transnational Organised Crime, which was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2000 and became effective on 28 January 2004. It is also referred to as the Smuggling Protocol;
4. Optional Protocol on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography, which is a Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child and requires parties to prohibit the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography. The

²⁵“What is Human Trafficking?”, available on: https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/human-trafficking/what-is-human-trafficking.html#What_is_Human_Trafficking

²⁶Global Report on Trafficking in Persons (Report). United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2018.

Protocol was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 2000 and became effective on 18 January 2002;

5.ILO Forced Labour Convention, 1930 (No. 29), whose full title is the Convention Concerning Forced or Compulsory Labour, 1930 (No.29), was adopted in Geneva on 28 June 1930 and became effective on 1st May 1932. Its object and purpose is to suppress the use of forced labour in all its forms irrespective of the nature of the work or the sector of activity in which it may be performed.

6.ILO Abolition of Forced Labour Convention, 1957 (No. 105), whose full title is Convention concerning the Abolition of Forced Labour, 1957 (No. 105), was adopted on 25 June 1957 and became effective on 17 January 1959. It cancels certain forms of forced labour still allowed under the Forced Labour Convention of 1930, such as punishment for strikes and as a punishment for holding certain political views;

7.ILO Minimum Age Convention, 1973 (No. 138) is adopted on 28 June 1973 and became effective on 19 June 1976. It requires ratifying states to pursue a national policy designed to ensure the effective abolition of child labour and to raise the minimum age for admission to employment or work progressively. Convention n°138 replaces several similar ILO conventions in specific fields of labour;

8.ILO Worst Forms of Child Labour Convention, 1999 (No.

182) concerns the Prohibition and Immediate Action for the Elimination of the Worst Forms of Child Labour, known in short as the Worst Forms of Child Labour Convention. It was adopted in Geneva on 17 June 1999 and became effective on 19 November 2000.

Nevertheless, not all these formal prohibitions by International law have prevented certain excesses in practice, through certain forms of modern slavery practiced by mafia networks and whose victims are mainly women and children from their own country.

1.6. Prohibition of certain forms of modern slavery:

Among these modern forms debt bondage, forced prostitution, forced marriage and child slavery. All of them fall under International law and are totally forbidden.

Debt bondage is the most common form of slavery today. It means the condition in which a person

“pledges him or herself against a loan of money, but the length and nature of the service is undefined, and the labour does not diminish the original debt” (Bales, 2000).

As a matter of fact, Debt bondage was included and defined as a form of slavery under the 1956 Supplementary Convention on Slavery. However, its many modern forms continue to include pawning, peonage and worker debt (Miers, 2000).

Debt bondage continues to exist in some countries all over the World and can be caused by different situations. For example, as a man may need a loan to finance a wedding, funeral, medicine, fertilizer, or a fine. Because the interest rates on these debts as

so high, debts are often inherited and children may replace their fathers or siblings.

Also, we can add the form of Forced prostitution to the list of forms of modern slavery. In fact, forced prostitution and sexual slavery are considered contemporary manifestations of this crime. They can be found anywhere in the world.

Forced marriage can also be considered a form of modern slavery, notably when the bride has no right or opportunity to refuse marriage. This form of marriage can result out of a kidnapping of girls in order to sell them as brides. Once married and raped, these girls are often kept under lock and key until they have a child, at which time they will be less likely to leave because they do not want to abandon their child (Miers, 2000).

Child slavery is considered a contemporary form of slavery as well, although it does come with debate as to what constitutes child slavery. However, child prostitution is widely considered a form of slavery in which children, mostly from South East Asia, South Asia and Latin America

“are sold by their parents either because they are destitute, have too many mouths to feed, or are simply greedy” (Miers, 2000).

People smuggling (also called human smuggling and migrant smuggling) is a related practice which is characterised by the consent of the person being smuggled²⁷. Smuggling situations can descend into human trafficking through coercion and

²⁷“Difference between Smuggling and Trafficking”, Anti-trafficking.net, 21 February 2013.

exploitation. Trafficked people are held against their will through acts of coercion, and forced to work for or provide services to the trafficker or others.

Furthermore, human trafficking is not to be confused with migrant smuggling (Obokata, 2019)²⁸. In accordance with the Protocol against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea and Air of 2000. According to article 3(a) of this text,

“smuggling is defined as: (t)he procurement, in order to obtain, directly or indirectly, a financial or other material benefit, of the illegal entry of a person into a state party of which the person is not a national or a permanent resident”.

1.7. Slavery and human trafficking as crimes against humanity:

The above list of Conventions, Resolutions and Protocols at the Universal level condemning and prohibiting slavery and human trafficking, can be completed by the Rome statute of 1998, that established the International Criminal Court (ICC). It was adopted in Rome, on 17 July 1998 and it became effective on 1st July 2002.

The article 7 of the Rome statute gives the definition of the “Crimes against humanity”. These are certain acts that are

²⁸It is evident that these two acts differ in some important respects. “For instance, there is no “means” element for smuggling. This suggests that those smuggled willingly take part in this process. It is also the case that the smuggling definition does not entail the “purpose element”, meaning that smuggling ends as soon as migrants reach their destinations, and that smugglers do not have the intention to exploit them or have no knowledge that they will be exploited by others (...). This in turn may justify tougher enforcement actions such as detention and deportation for smuggled migrants, while protection will be high on the agenda for trafficked victims. It is important to remember, however, that a clear distinction between trafficking and smuggling cannot be drawn in many cases. The latter can be the beginning of the former, and many migrants experience a wide variety of abuses during their journey (...).”

purposely committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian or an identifiable part of a civilian population. Unlike war crimes, crimes against humanity can be committed during peace or war. They are not isolated or sporadic events, but are part either of a government policy (although the perpetrators need not identify themselves with this policy) or of a wide practice of atrocities tolerated or condoned by a government or a de facto authority (Truche, 1992; Zoller, 1993; Robinson, 1999; Zakr, 2001; Jurovicsw, 2002; Roulot, 2002; Luban, 2004; Currat, 2006; De Guzman, 2011; Gueldich, 2011).

Among other crimes, Article 7 of the treaty stated that:

“For the purpose of this Statute, “crimes against humanity” means any of the following acts when committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian population, with knowledge of the attack: (c) Enslavement; (...); (g) Rape, sexual slavery, enforced prostitution, forced pregnancy, enforced sterilisation, or any other form of sexual violence of comparable gravity (...).”

In the light of this article 7, only slavery is considered as a crime against humanity. What about human trafficking? As a matter of fact, in this text, other conducts included under the “Crimes against humanity”, such as forced pregnancy or sexual slavery, as well as enforced disappearance could also resonate well with human trafficking.

“However, in order for trafficking to be regarded as any of these crimes against humanity, the relevant criteria (e.g. widespread or systematic nature, knowledge of the attack, and being part of an organisational policy) must be proven and this will inevitably limit the scope of its application in practice” (Obokata, 2005).

Aside from the above mentioned instruments, International human rights law has made important contributions to addressing this crime. This makes us realize that human trafficking is not only an international crime, but also a violation of the human rights of victims (Bassiouni, 1996).

This is to affirm that slavery and human trafficking are definitely considered as “Crimes against humanity”. They are peremptory norms that have no exception. Moreover, when committed as part of a widespread or systematic attack directed against any civilian population, with knowledge of the attack, their authors are answerable before the International Criminal Court (ICC) for crimes against humanity.

The United Nations Subcommittee on the impunity of human rights violations had, by Resolution 2002/5 of 12 August 2002, asked that

“crimes against humanity and other flagrant and massive violations of human rights that are inalienable should be prosecuted before the courts (...)”²⁹.

On the other hand, and according to the conclusions of the Chapter V related to the “Peremptory norms of general law (Jus Cogens)”, it is obvious that the ban of slavery and human trafficking is a norm of jus cogens.

Also, according to the Conclusion 4 Criteria for the identification of a peremptory norm of general international law

²⁹HNUDH Resolution, 2002/5, Human rights Sub-committee: Recognition of responsibility and reparation for massive and flagrant violations of human rights which constitute crimes against humanity and which took place during the period of slavery, colonialism and wars of conquest, 12 August 2002.

(jus cogens):

“To identify a peremptory norm of general international law (jus cogens), it is necessary to establish that the norm in question meets the following criteria: (a) it is a norm of general international law; and (b) it is accepted and recognised by the international community of states as a whole as a norm from which no derogation is permitted and which can be modified only by a subsequent norm of general international law having the same character”³⁰ and on the light of all the universal instruments above, we can confirm again that the prohibition of slavery and human trafficking is a norm of general international law, accepted and recognised by the international community as a norm from which no derogation is permitted.

Furthermore, according to the Conclusion 5 Bases for peremptory norms of general international law (jus cogens)

“1. Customary international law is the most common basis for peremptory norms of general international law (Jus cogens). 2. Treaty provisions and general principles of law may also serve as bases for peremptory norms of general international law (Jus cogens)”³¹, there is no doubt that the prohibition of slavery and human trafficking is included in all the legal instruments related to this latter.

Besides the universal instruments, we can also list the regional ones at the regional and continental levels.

2. The International framework at the regional level:

Human trafficking and slavery are not only condemned as a violation of human rights by International universal conventions. The complex and transnational nature of human

30A/74/10, conclusion 4, page 142.

31A/74/10, conclusion 5, page 158.

trafficking in the World requires an integrated response and the role of regional organisations becomes more and more important, as they can contribute to the strengthening of both individual and collective actions against this crime.

In this regard, we will focus on the European and the African experiences in abolishing and prohibiting slavery and human trafficking on these two respective continents. By doing that, we are also demonstrating that these norms are peremptory norms that are accepted and recognised by the International community of states as a whole and that can have no derogations at all.

2.1.A the European level:

The European Convention on Human Rights, which was signed in Rome on 4 November 1950 and became effective on 3 September 1953, provides, in its Article 4 on “Prohibition of Slavery and Forced labour”³² the following:

“1.No one shall be held in slavery or servitude.

2.No one shall be required to perform forced or compulsory labour.

3.For the purpose of this Article the term “forced or compulsory labour” shall not include: (a) any work required to be done in the ordinary course of detention imposed according to the provisions of Article 5 [right to liberty and security] of this Convention or during conditional release from such detention; (b) any service of a military character or, in case of conscientious objectors in countries where they are recognised, service exacted instead of compulsory military service; (c) any service exacted in case of an emergency or calamity threatening the life or well-being of the community; (d) any work or service which forms part of normal civic obligations”.

This article 4 of ECHR provides an absolute prohibition of

³²Guide on Article 4 of the Convention – Prohibition of slavery and forced labour, European Court of Human rights, Updated on 31 December 2019, The Case-Law Guides are available at: www.echr.coe.int (Case-law-Case-law analysis-Case law guides).

slavery, including human trafficking, servitude, forced or compulsory labour.

“It also requires High Contracting States to fulfill positive obligations such as having appropriate legislative and administrative framework, protective measures and providing an effective, independent and prompt investigation besides negative obligation not to cause any violations (...)” (Uncular, 2016). In addition to that, the Committee of Ministers adopted the Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings (CETS No. 197), on 3 May 2005 and became effective on 1st February 2008.

The Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings (CETS No. 197), the first European treaty in this field, is a comprehensive treaty focusing mainly on the protection of victims of trafficking and the safeguard of their rights. It also aims to prevent trafficking and to prosecute traffickers. In addition, the Convention provides for the setting up of an effective and independent monitoring mechanism capable of controlling the implementation of the obligations contained in the Convention.

Article 1, related to the “Purposes of the Convention”, provides that:

“1. The purposes of this Convention are: a. to prevent and combat trafficking in human beings, while guaranteeing gender equality; b. to protect the human rights of the victims of trafficking, design a comprehensive framework for the protection and assistance of victims and witnesses, while guaranteeing gender equality, as well as to ensure effective investigation and prosecution; c. to promote international cooperation on action against trafficking in human beings. 2. In order to ensure effective implementation of its provisions by the Parties, this Convention sets up a specific monitoring mechanism”.

According to Article 2, related to the “Scope of the

Convention”,

“This Convention shall apply to all forms of trafficking in human beings, whether national or transnational, whether or not connected with organised crime”.

Article 36 of this Convention established the Group of Experts on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings (GRETA³³), which is the monitoring mechanism on human trafficking established by the Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings. It stipulates that GRETA can have from 10 to 15 members of independent and impartial experts from a variety of backgrounds. They have been chosen from amongst nationals of the states parties to the Convention and are known for their competence and professional experience in the areas covered by the Convention; the term of office is four years, renewable once. The current composition of GRETA reflects a gender and geographical balance.

The Group is responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the Convention by the parties, following a procedure divided in rounds. At the beginning of each round, GRETA defines autonomously the provisions to be monitored and determines the most appropriate means to carry out the evaluation, being guided by the Rules of Procedure for Evaluating Implementation of the Convention. In addition, GRETA regularly publishes general reports on its activities.

Complementary protection against sex trafficking of children is

³³<https://www.coe.int/en/web/anti-human-trafficking/greta>

ensured through the Council of Europe Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse, signed in Lanzarote, on 25 October 2007. The Convention became effective on 1st July 2010.

Besides, human trafficking is subject to a Directive in the European Union

“Directive 2011/36/eu of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2011 on preventing and combating trafficking in human beings and protecting its victims and replacing Council Framework Decision 2002/629/JH”³⁴.

2.2. At the African level:

There is actually not a specific instrument prohibiting slavery and human trafficking in the African context. However, the African legal framework on human and people's rights can be mentioned. Especially, the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (called the Banjul Charter), which was adopted on 27 June 1981 and became effective on 21 October 1986, that prohibits slavery and human trafficking. In fact, article 4 of the Banjul Charter provides that:

“Every individual shall have the right to the respect of the dignity inherent in a human being and to the recognition of his legal status. All forms of exploitation and degradation of man particularly slavery, slave trade, torture, cruel, inhuman or degrading punishment and treatment shall be prohibited”.

The Banjul Charter is beefed up by the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the African Child of 1st July 1990 and the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa of 1st July 2003, which make

³⁴Eur-lex.europa.eu.

specific provisions on the protection of women and children against slavery.

In this regard, article 29 of the Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the African Child of 1st July 1990 and which became effective on 29 November 2009, entitled “Sale, Trafficking and Abduction”, provides that:

“state parties to the present Charter shall take appropriate measures to prevent: (a) the abduction, sale of, or traffic in children for any purpose or in any form, by any person including parents or legal guardians of the child; (b) the use of children in all forms of begging”.

On the other hand, article 4 paragraph 1 of the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and People’s Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa of 1st July 2003 and which became effective on 25 November 2005, entitled “The Rights to Life, Integrity and Security of the Person”, provides that:

“Every woman shall be entitled to respect for her life and the integrity and security of her person. All forms of exploitation, cruel, inhuman or degrading punishment and treatment shall be prohibited”.

Moreover, the Ouagadougou Action Plan to Combat Trafficking in Human Beings, Especially Women and Children of November 2006 reaffirms international instruments on human trafficking and encourages African states to adopt legislative, administrative and institutional measures to combat trafficking in human beings. These measures include the formulation and implementation of national action plans and regional action plans by African states to provide for comprehensive and coordinated interventions.

There are also sub-regional efforts to combat human trafficking such as the ECOWAS³⁵ Initial Plan of Action against Trafficking in Persons (2002-2003), the joint ECOWAS/ECCAS Regional Plan of Action to Combat Trafficking in Persons, especially Women and Children (2006-2009) and the SADC³⁶ Regional Plan of Action on Trafficking in Persons (2009-2019).

Furthermore, we can confirm,

“The desirability of enacting a specific law on human trafficking, which include a comprehensive definition in line with the Trafficking Protocol, has been repeatedly expressed by human rights bodies. It should be highlighted in this regard that many African states, particularly those that are partially or wholly based on the common law tradition, have done so. For others, which are influenced by the civil law tradition and/or rely on general Penal Codes, certain aspects of trafficking such as enslavement, prostitution, sale/purchase of slaves are covered. However, these are not always in line with the international standards as mentioned above, and this will provide an opportunity for the African Court to encourage them to make necessary amendments and facilitate a more integrated response across the region (...)” (Obokata, 2019).

Above and beyond, it is important to mention that the African Union Commission on International Law (AUCIL) (Kilangi, 2013; Tchikaya, 2013)³⁷ had initiated a study to prepare an African Convention on the prohibition of slavery. The Draft

³⁵ECOWAS is the Economic Community of West African States.

³⁶SADC is Southern African Development Community.

³⁷The African Union Commission on International Law (AUCIL) was created in 2009 as an independent advisory organ in accordance with article 5(2) of the AU Constitutive Act. The Statute of the AUCIL was adopted by the 12th Ordinary Session of the Assembly of the African Union held in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia from 1 to 4 February 2009. The AUCIL started work on 3rd May 2010 the effective date for the term of office of the pioneer members of the AUCIL. The mandate of the AUCIL falls under five (5) broad categories, namely (i) the progressive development of international law, (ii) the codification of international law; (iii) contribution to the objectives and principles of the Union; (iv) revision of treaties; and (v) encouraging the teaching, study, dissemination and wider appreciation of international law.

convention (a text of 16 articles) prepared by the Special Rapporteur, Professor Sebastiao DA SILVA ISATA³⁸ was presented to the AUCIL Plenary during the 17th ordinary session of the AUCIL which was held in Addis Ababa from 25 March to 4 April 2019³⁹. The examination and adoption of this Draft convention in its first reading was done during the 18th session of the AUCIL held in Addis Ababa from 18 to 29 November 2019⁴⁰. The Plenary decided to have further discussions and a second reading during its next 19th ordinary session.

Also, the African Union Commission on International Law (AUCIL) was seized on 27 July 2010 by the Executive Council of the African Union, in the Kampala Assembly session, to conduct research and appropriate studies on reparations for the crimes and misdeeds of Negro slave trade, the transatlantic slave trade and its consequences. At its second ordinary session in 2011, the AUCIL appointed a Special Rapporteur, Professor Blaise TCHIKAYA, to appraise on behalf of the Commission the current state of studies and research on the subject. He has conducted field research and interviewed many specialists, researchers, historians and certain scientific authorities on the

³⁸Prof. Sebastiao Da Silva Isata (Angola) was elected as an AUCIL member in 2015, re-elected in 2020. He is the current Chairperson of the AUCIL.

³⁹Activity report of the African Union Commission on International law (AUCIL) for the period January-December 2019, paragraphs 27 and 28.

⁴⁰Activity report of the African Union Commission on International law (AUCIL), 18th ordinary session held in Addis Ababa from 18 to 29 November 2019.

subject. The Commission's research was punctuated by three preliminary reports presented by its Special Rapporteur, which were the subject of extensive debate in plenary and in working groups. This study was submitted and presented, in its totality, to the AUCIL plenary during the tenth ordinary session of the AUCIL that took place from 13 to 24 April 2015 in Addis Ababa⁴¹.

In the conclusions of its study on

“The juridical basis for reparations for transatlantic slavery and other damages to the African continent”,

the special Rapporteur concluded that:

“After three years of work (2010-2013), the AUCIL notes that many pertinent elements of International law exist, among which are International conventions, jurisprudence and doctrine. The said elements backstop Executive Council directive and serve as its justification and foundations. The enslavement of Africans which is a fact generating a long-standing liability arises, in the opinion of historians from four centuries of damage and sufferings caused to African communities (...)” (Tchikaya, 2015).

With regard to this fact, the AUCIL observed, following the work of the United Nations International Law Commission in respect of international responsibility, that it was necessary for the lawfulness of the generating fact to be obvious.

The AUCIL did not reach the conclusion that the states from whose territory, slave ships were leaving for trafficking of

⁴¹This study was not examined yet by the STC (Specialized technical committee) of the AU on justice and legal affairs. The STC on justice and legal affairs has the following powers and functions: considering AU draft treaties and other legal instruments or documents; surveying international law with a view to selecting topics for codification within AU legal frameworks; following up on issues concerning the signature, ratification/accession, domestication and implementation of OAU/AU treaties. All STCs and the AU Commission on International Law (AUCIL) submit their proposed legal instruments to the STC for further consideration.

Africans did their utmost to halt this criminal phenomenon. The attention of the AUCIL was drawn to the fact that the acts of slavery should be punished on the basis of the obligation of due diligence.

During its deliberations, the AUCIL also had to address a common law principle:

“Any act of a human being, which causes damage to another human being obliges the person by whose fault the damage occurred to make reparations therefore”⁴².

According to the conclusions of the special Rapporteur “The mission of the Commission was to identify the issue and assert its legal basis” (Tchikaya, 2015). He added that: “The global context is conducive for a comprehensive African initiative for reparations” (Tchikaya, 2015) and that the “AUCIL proposes that no form of reparation, material or moral, should be discarded” (Tchikaya, 2015). He also argued that:

“The rules of international society are not limited to any form of reparation as the most effective in this regard. There is satisfaction as a way to extinguish a liability if the parties so wish. It is in fact possible to combine the two forms of reparation. A world conference should clarify this point” (Tchikaya, 2015).

According to the special Rapporteur of this specific study, the goal of the recommendations is:

“the adoption by the Assembly of the Union of a resolution that emphasizes the need for a firm commitment on the part of the 54 Member States. The

⁴²This principle is applicable in the major European systems. Slavery is also perpetrated by individuals or private companies. To whom are the damages arising from the evils of slavery to be attributed? “The Commission concluded that the issue was not, at this stage that of determining on which of the states or slave trade companies or indeed individuals concerned would devolve the obligation for reparations”, *Idem. op. cit.* paragraph 56.

Conference should support the universal principle according to which any damage presupposes reparation, and in consequence, should accede to reparation for the misdeeds arising from crime against humanity, namely, the enslavement of Africans. The AUCIL proposed that a World conference on reparations for the harm inflicted by the transatlantic slavery and its consequences should be organised in 2016. A Special African Union Administrator for African history, slave trade and reparations should be appointed for administrative coverage of these new commitments and the great periods in the history of our societies⁴³.

In order to better respond to the request of the Assembly of the Union made at its session in Kampala in July 2010 for a study to be conducted with recommendations on reparations to Africa on account of the adverse consequences of trafficking in black people and slavery and pursuant to Article 5 of its Statute on progressive development of International law, which requires that a questionnaire should be distributed to Member States inviting them to provide it with information on the issues at stake, the Special Rapporteur also prepared a questionnaire to ask the African Countries some questions related to the conceptual aspects⁴⁴, the organisational and diplomatic aspects of reparation⁴⁵ and on aspects relating to the content and forms

⁴³*Idem.* op. cit paragraph 63.

⁴⁴These questions are the following: 1. Is it in your opinion appropriate today to raise the question of reparations to Africa for reasons of the adverse consequences of the triangular trade, trafficking of black people and slavery? 2. What misdeeds are in your view attributable to the triangular trade, the phenomenon of trafficking and slavery in your country? 3. What historical marks and vestiges have been left by the triangular trade and the slave trade in your country? 4. Are there "places of memory" on slavery and the triangular trade in your country? 5. Does your national law contain provisions or statements on the triangular trade, the phenomenon of trafficking and slavery in your country? 6. In the perspective of reparations, how should one perceive African countries' involvement in the triangular trade and slavery?

⁴⁵These questions are the following: 1. Do you consider it appropriate to convene an international conference for a global debate on reparations to Africa?

of reparation⁴⁶.

As we demonstrated above, the International legal framework prohibiting slavery and human trafficking, at both universal and regional levels, is more than sufficient to consider this crime as a part of the peremptory norms of general International law (*jus cogens*).

This is to say how important the respect and the enforcement of this legal framework at the national laws of all the countries should be. This is also to confirm the importance of International mechanisms of prevention and protection in order to reinforce and/or control this respect.

The institutional protection: numerous international organisations defending victims of slavery and human trafficking

As the primary actors of international law, states have the primary obligation to combat slavery and human trafficking. There are mainly three obligations imposed upon a state in case

⁴⁶These questions are the following: 1. Did your country have to press historical demands similar to compensation claims because of the nefarious consequences of slave trade and slavery? 2. Of what type was the reparation? Indicate the outcomes. 3. International law recognises “satisfaction” as a means of damage reparation. Is it in your opinion possible to use satisfaction or solemn declaration of historical responsibility, which is one of the forms, as an expression of reparations to Africa on account of slave trade and slavery? 4. What is your view about monetary compensation? 5. What pecuniary evaluation could be undertaken on the adverse consequences of the triangular trade, slave trade and slavery? 6. Should African States accept as reparations, architectural constructions, monuments or extensive training and enlightenment programmes on the history of slavery?

of slavery and human trafficking. The first is to prohibit and prosecute slavery and human trafficking. The second is the protection of the victims of slavery and human trafficking⁴⁷. The third is the prevention of slavery and human trafficking.

Nevertheless, when states do not assume their duties under International law, the universal system of human rights protection is mainly the system established by the United Nations. This system is based on a number of general and specific international legal instruments (as presented in the section above).

Moreover, the protection of this International legal framework dealing with the prohibition of slavery and human trafficking requires, on the one hand, a universal consensus around the acceptance of these rights (through the ratification of these International legal instruments) and on the other hand, institutional mechanisms that can be either dependent on International organisations, in particular the United Nations (1), or on NGOs, in particular humanitarian NGOs (2).

1. The human rights bodies of protection within the United Nations:

Actually, the role of the United Nations is undeniable in the

⁴⁷Under International Human rights law, the obligation to protect the victims of Human trafficking is derived from a general duty to secure, ensure or restore rights as well as to provide remedies. Cfr. Resolution 20/1, Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children: Access to Effective Remedies for Trafficked Persons and Their Right to an Effective Remedy for Human Rights Violations, A/HRC/20/L1 (June 2012).

protection of human rights, especially when someone is a victim of slavery or human trafficking. This is the international and universal organization, which brings together almost all the states of the world. Its goals and objectives being based on international peace and security as well as respect for human rights, it goes without saying that it is the best equipped to achieve these goals and objectives.

In terms of protection measures, although international and regional human right instruments do not provide for a specific list for the victims, human rights bodies are developing certain guidance as part of the prohibition of slavery, or other relevant provisions.

In addition, we have to mention the United Nations Human Rights Council⁴⁸ which, since 2006, has been the main intergovernmental organ of the United Nations on all questions relating to human rights, made up of 47 states, which are responsible for strengthen the promotion and protection of human rights around the globe. The UNHRC investigates allegations of breaches of human rights in United Nations member states and addresses important thematic human rights

⁴⁸The *Human Rights Council* is an inter-governmental body within the United Nations system made up of 47 states in charge of the promotion and protection of all human rights around the globe. It has the ability to discuss all thematic Human rights issues and situations that require its attention throughout the year. It meets at the UN Office at Geneva. It was created by the United Nations General Assembly on 15 March 2006 by resolution 60/251, see: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/hrbodies/hrc/pages/home.aspx>

issues. The Human Rights Council replaced the former United Nations Commission on Human Rights.

On the other hand, we can mention the Human Rights Committee⁴⁹, which is governed by the International Covenant on Civil, and Political Rights (ICCPR), which became effective on 23 March 1976. The ICCPR outlines, in part IV, the obligations of states to uphold the freedom from slavery. All states are required to submit regular reports to the Committee on how the rights of the Covenant are being implemented. A state's initial report must be within one year of acceding the Covenant and after this, whenever the Committee requests a report (usually every four years). In addition to the submission of reports, article 41 of the Covenant makes it possible for the Committee to consider inter-state complaints, and furthermore, the First Optional Protocol to the Covenant gives the Committee the capacity to investigate individual complaints with regards to violations of the Covenant by state parties.

Furthermore, the International Labour Organisation⁵⁰, in addition to the efforts of the International Labour Rights Fund⁵¹ and the International Organisation for Migration⁵², is devoted to promoting social justice and internationally recognised human

49<https://www.ohchr.org/en/hrbodies/ccpr/pages/ccprindex.aspx>

50<https://www.ilo.org/global/about-the-ilo/mission-and-objectives/lang--en/index.htm>

51www.laborrights.org

52www.iom.int

and labour rights, pursuing its founding mission that social justice is essential to universal and lasting peace.

There is also the 2010 UN Global Plan of Action to Combat Trafficking in Persons, a General Assembly resolution⁵³, calling for global, regional and sub-regional efforts and cooperation in the prevention of trafficking, protection of victims of trafficking and the prosecution of crimes of trafficking. The UN Office of Drugs and Crime (UNODC)⁵⁴, established in 1997, is the lead UN agency to address human trafficking and is also the guardian of related international instruments in this regard.

Member States also adopted resolution A/RES/68/192 and designated July 30 as the “World Day for the fight against Trafficking in Persons”. This resolution declared that such a day was necessary to

“raise awareness of the situation of victims of human trafficking and for the promotion and protection of their rights”⁵⁵.

For example, on the 2019 World Day, UNODC was focusing on highlighting the importance of Government action in the interest

⁵³A/RES/64/293, *2010 UN Global Plan of Action to Combat Trafficking in Persons*.

⁵⁴www.unodc.org

⁵⁵According to the resolution A/RES/68/192, 14 February 2014 on “Improving the coordination of efforts against trafficking in persons”, the General Assembly decided that: “Also decides, in the context of the need for raising awareness of the situation of victims of human trafficking and for the promotion and protection of their rights, to designate 30 July as the World Day against Trafficking in Persons, to be observed every year as from 2014, invites all Member States, relevant agencies of the United Nations system and other international organisations, as well as civil society, to observe the World Day, and notes that the costs of all activities that may arise should be met from voluntary contributions”, (paragraph 5). <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N13/450/97/PDF/N1345097.pdf?OpenElement>

of victims of trafficking. But the call to action is not only to Governments, everyone was encouraged to take action to prevent this heinous crime, as to be informed by downloading the brochure on this year's theme and on UNODC's work on human trafficking; share, like and comment on the social media messages for the World Day; and Donate to the United Nations Voluntary Trust Fund for Victims of Human Trafficking, which provides on-the-ground assistance and protection to victims of trafficking⁵⁶.

The United Nations Voluntary Trust Fund for Victims of Human Trafficking⁵⁷ provides

“assistance each year to thousands of people who have experienced some form of slavery. It is a privilege to meet both the people concerned and the organisations that provide the assistance to them, located in every continent of the world” (Vaz Cabral, 2006).

Since its establishment by the General Assembly in 1991 (resolution 46/122), the Slavery Fund has supported more than 400 organisations in 95 countries, providing rehabilitation and assistance to thousands of victims. The Fund is managed by the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, with the advice of a Board of Trustees composed of independent experts from the five world regions. The Board meets once a year to determine priorities, review policies and adopt recommendations on grants (Vaz Cabral, 2006).

⁵⁶<https://www.unodc.org/endht/>

⁵⁷<https://www.ohchr.org/EN/Issues/Slavery/UNVTF/FCFS/Pages/WhattheFundis.aspx>

Moreover, the Resolution adopted by the Human Rights Council on 26 September 2019⁵⁸ concerning the Decision 42/10 related to the “Special Rapporteur on contemporary forms of slavery, including its causes and consequences”, *inter alia* decided the following:

“Welcomes the work and the thematic reports of the Special Rapporteur on contemporary forms of Slavery, including its causes and consequences, including those on the impact of slavery and servitude on marginalised migrant women workers in the global domestic economy and on current and emerging forms of Slavery”⁵⁹;
decided also that:

“the Special Rapporteur shall continue to examine and report on all contemporary forms of slavery and slavery-like practices, but in particular those defined in the Slavery Convention of 1926 and the Supplementary Convention on the Abolition of Slavery, Slave Trade, and Institutions and Practices Similar to Slavery of 1956, and all other issues covered previously by the Working Group on Contemporary Forms of Slavery (etc.)”⁶⁰.

On the other hand, the consecration and consolidation of an International criminal justice which is competent in the event of violation of these rights remains the most effective guarantor to prevent and punish such violations. In this context, universal international courts play an important role in this protection. In addition to the International Court of Justice (ICJ), which is the main judicial organ of the United Nations and enjoying two kinds of jurisdiction: contentious jurisdiction and advisory jurisdiction, there is also the International Criminal Court (ICC)

⁵⁸A/HRC/RES/42/10, Resolution adopted by the Human Rights Council on 26 September 2019.

⁵⁹A/HRC/RES/42/10, Resolution adopted by the Human Rights Council on 26 September 2019, paragraph 1.

⁶⁰A/HRC/RES/42/10, Resolution adopted by the Human Rights Council on 26 September 2019, paragraph 5.

created by the 1998 Rome Statute, which became effective in 2002. It is competent in cases of International crimes (genocide, war crimes, crimes against humanity and crime of aggression). It can only try a case if national jurisdictions are unable or refuse to prosecute. In other words, the International Criminal Court (ICC) can step in when states are unwilling or unable to investigate, prosecute and punish human trafficking effectively at the national level.

In addition to the ICC, regional international courts have been created. Three of them have a particularly important role in the defence and protection of human rights. These are the Court of Justice of the European Union, the European Court of Human Rights⁶¹, the Inter-American Court of Human Rights, but also the African Court on Human and People's Rights, in spite of the number of challenges that can face it (Obokata, 2019)⁶².

⁶¹The European Court of Human Rights of the Council of Europe in Strasbourg has passed judgments concerning trafficking in human beings which violated obligations under the European Convention on Human Rights. See *Siliadin v. France*, judgment of 26 July 2005, and *Rantsev v. Cyprus and Russia*, judgment of 7 January 2010.

⁶²For instance, "a very large number of traffickers, including organised criminal groups, commit this crime in Africa, and it is doubtful whether the African Court will have sufficient financial, human and other resources to conduct effective investigations and prosecutions, bearing in mind other crimes it will have to deal with. The Court will be required to prioritise, and the extent to which human trafficking will come before others is not clear. It may well decide to address it through state responsibility instead, as that will encourage Member States to respond more proactively at the national level. The same reasoning is applicable to the number of victims. If they are to take part in criminal proceedings against traffickers, the African Court must be able to provide sufficient support such as witness protection, legal assistance, translation and/or interpretation and any other assistance, which may be required by them. As the victims of a heinous crime, they should also be entitled to compensation. In the end, it may not be an effective use of its limited resources for the

There is also the United Nations Security Council which is a military body capable of protecting human rights and empowered to take concrete measures (even military actions including the use of force) to maintain or restore International peace and security, especially in the context of the implementation of the concept of “Responsibility to protect”⁶³, as a response to crimes against humanity.

In addition, it should be noted that the efforts undertaken at the UN level, although laudable, remain insufficient. Flagrant violations of the most basic human rights, especially crimes of slavery and human trafficking, continue to take place, despite the work and huge efforts of all these institutions. Consequently, all these efforts must be complemented by the work of NGOs and civil society in the protection of human rights, which are more denouncing and have a wider impact compared to institutions from state sources.

2. The International Institutions of protection within the NGOs:

We never do enough to defend human rights and despite the favourable spirit of human rights at the time, many violations and attacks are still recorded today with impunity.

Consequently, the inability of national and international mechanisms to ensure sufficient protection of human rights and

African Court to exercise criminal jurisdiction over human trafficking (...).

⁶³The Responsibility to protect, Report of the International Commission on Intervention and State Sovereignty, December 2001, <http://responsibilitytoprotect.org/ICISS%20Report.pdf>

public freedoms is at the root of the birth of a significant number of non-governmental organisations (NGOs) which have contributed, thanks to their persistent action, to denounce and limit the violations of these rights.

There is no doubt that if human rights law has taken on such importance in recent decades, it is largely due to the militant activity of non-governmental human rights organisations. Several of them have recently started to refer to humanitarian law, in order to support their action and it is very likely that they will have a considerable influence in the future.

In this sense, the number of NGOs whose activity is oriented towards the promotion, defence and protection of human rights, including actions in favour of refugees, migrants and victims of human trafficking, is impressive⁶⁴. Nevertheless, we can review the examples of the most globally known humanitarian NGOs and Anti-trafficking initiatives to end human trafficking and protect victims. Among the ones known globally Amnesty International⁶⁵, Human Rights Watch⁶⁶ and Save The Children⁶⁷. Actually, Anti-trafficking awareness and fundraising campaigns constitute a significant portion of anti-trafficking initiatives. In

⁶⁴The List of United Nations Agencies, Programmes, NGOs and Foundations working on Contemporary Forms of Slavery had been published by the UN Human rights Office of the High Commissioner on the following link:

<https://www.ohchr.org/EN/Issues/Slavery/UNVTFCFS/Pages/SlaveryList.aspx>

⁶⁵www.amnesty.org

⁶⁶www.hrw.org

⁶⁷www.saveaslave.com

this regard, we can cite the following, which are specialised in defending people who are victims of slavery, modern slavery, human trafficking and other contemporary forms of slavery:

Anti-slavery⁶⁸ which had built an anti-slavery movement in collaboration with service providers, law enforcement agencies, NGOs, trade unions, lawyers, businesses and government authorities, in order to support tens of thousands of adults and children affected by slavery every year, to gain and keep their freedom, as well as to campaign to change the social, economic, legal and political systems that trap them. They adapt their response to the local context in all countries they work in. In Niger, it builds schools and projects for communities that escaped their traditional masters; in Mauritania it provides education and microloans to women rebuilding their lives in freedom; in Senegal, it works with whole communities to protect children from local schools from being forced to beg. Moreover, they lobbied national governments to improve their response to slavery practices, campaigned to introduce anti-slavery laws, and challenged governments in courts when they fail to protect their citizens from the effects of slavery.

Free the slaves⁶⁹, since its establishment in 2000, is considered as a leader and pioneer in the modern abolitionist movement. They had helped awaken the world to the fact that slavery still

68www.antislavery.org

69www.freetheclaves.net

exists, why it does, and where it is worse. They developed a global blueprint for change to inform governments, international institutions, faith communities, businesses, and the public of what they can do. They are also implementing their community-based strategy in strategically selected countries, demonstrating that their model works and that it is both scalable and replicable. They inform their policy advocacy to strengthen anti-slavery laws and rid slavery from manufacturing supply chains and business practices. They help communities chart their own path toward sustainable freedom based on their unique needs and circumstances, and strengthen the capacity of grassroots organisations, government agencies, advocacy coalitions, and the media to take action. They support vulnerable communities through education, mobilisation, and increasing access to education, vocational training, and essential services. They rescue those in slavery and help them rejoin their families and communities. They record and share success stories so that the world can see what both slavery and freedom look like. Free the slaves co-implements all community projects with and through locally-based organisations.

Save a slave⁷⁰ is a link on Website that helps raising awareness of modern day slavery, trafficking and forced prostitution. The Save a slave website was created for the purposes of providing

⁷⁰www.saveaslave.com

information to interested parties and is open to the general public over the Internet, as well as to organisations or individuals that fight modern day slavery.

Committee Against Modern Slavery⁷¹ (CCEM), since its establishment in 1994, has been fighting all forms of human trafficking for the purpose of labour exploitation, including domestic work. It provides social and legal assistance to victims throughout France and denounces these situations all over the world. Its mission is to shelter, protect and defend victims. To this end, it fights for the prosecution and the conviction of the authors, appeals to the public authorities and raises public awareness.

Coalition against Trafficking in Women⁷², since its establishment in 1988, has been working to end the trafficking and sexual exploitation of women and girls by advocating for strong laws and policies, raising public awareness and supporting survivor leadership globally. In order to achieve equality and a world in which no sex trafficking and sexual exploitation exists, they call on governments at all levels to enact strong laws and policies based on principles of women's rights and human rights. They also raise awareness about these issues as forms of sex-based and gender-based violence and partner to create systemic change.

⁷¹www.esclavagemoderne.org

⁷²www.catwinternational.org

Project to end Human Trafficking⁷³ (PEHT) is a non-profit organisation that was founded in 2004, as part of the anti-slavery movement. The initial goal of the founders was not to begin an organisation, but simply to offer educational lectures about human trafficking. The Project to End Human Trafficking (PEHT) is managed entirely by volunteers. As part of the antislavery movement, PEHT was founded in 2004 by Dr. Mary C. BURKE and several of her former graduate students at Carlow University. At the time, it was one of only three organisations in the United States dedicated exclusively to anti-human trafficking work. Now PEHT consistently receives requests from the United States and abroad for general information sessions as well as for specialised training for professionals who are likely to come into contact with a victim or survivor. The Project to End Human Trafficking works towards the prevention and elimination of trafficking in persons through awareness raising, direct service coordination, capacity building and collaboration with key stakeholders.

Global Alliance Against Trafficking in Women⁷⁴ (GAATW) is an Alliance of more than 80 non-governmental organisations from Africa, Asia, Europe, LAC and North America. Member Organisations include migrant rights organisations; anti-trafficking organisations; self-organised groups of migrant

⁷³www.endhumantrafficking.org

⁷⁴www.gaatw.org

workers, domestic workers, survivors of trafficking and sex workers; human rights and women's rights organisations; and direct service providers. GAATW sees the phenomenon of human trafficking intrinsically embedded in the context of migration for the purpose of labour. It therefore promotes and defends the human rights of all migrants and their families against the threat of an increasingly globalised labour market and calls for safety standards for migrant workers in the process of migration and in the formal and informal work sectors, garment and food processing, agriculture and farming, domestic work, sex work, where slavery-like conditions and practices exist. GAATW is committed to bringing change at the local level through its Members and allies, and internationally through the work of the International Secretariat and GAATW's special consultative status to the Economic and Social Council of the United Nations (ECOSOC).

Human Trafficking Search (National Multicultural Institute)⁷⁵ (HTS) seeks to raise awareness and help prevent and eliminate human trafficking worldwide. HTS creates a weekly blog, publishes research, and hosts a global resource database on human trafficking and modern-day slavery. Launched in 2006, the global database has grown to manage thousands of multilingual resources from around the world. They cover topics

⁷⁵www.humantraffickingsearch.net

that include forced and bonded labour, sex trafficking, child trafficking, forced marriage, and more. Human Trafficking Search is the flagship project of the O.L. PATHY Family Foundation (OLP), a private foundation that strives to promote innovative solutions to Human trafficking.

Coalition to Abolish Slavery and Trafficking⁷⁶ (CAST) is a Los Angeles-based non-profit organisation that is working to put an end to modern slavery and human trafficking through comprehensive, life-transforming services to survivors and a platform to advocate for groundbreaking policies and legislation. Over the past two decades, CAST has supported thousands of survivors through every phase of their journey to freedom from counselling, to legal resources, to housing, educational and leadership training and mentorship. Through these programs, CAST has helped empower survivors to overcome their traumatic pasts and become leading voices in shaping policy and public awareness to ultimately put an end to the fastest growing criminal enterprise of the 21st century. CAST is one of the pioneers of the US anti-trafficking movement. The organisation was founded by Dr. Kathryn McMAHON and a group of community activists, in response to the discovery of 72 Thai workers that had been kept for seven years in slavery and debt bondage in Los Angeles.

⁷⁶www.castla.org

Conclusion and recommendations

Modern slavery constitutes a gross violation of human rights. It is also considered a major threat to global economic and political development, democracy and peace. Some of the factors that encourage human trafficking and other transnational crimes are poverty and global inequality. Poor people and citizens of developing countries are most vulnerable for trafficking.

The high levels of poverty, unemployment, corruption and armed conflicts coupled with low levels of education and awareness and lack of good governance, contribute to the existing challenges of slavery and human trafficking in the World and weaken efforts taken to combat these crimes. Many victims of trafficking also tend to move from poor areas to rich ones and many are lured by promises of a better life.

Nowadays, in spite of all the International legal instruments, international organisations and initiatives who are struggling in order to prevent, protect and prosecute acts of slavery and human trafficking, these crimes still continue to occur in different countries. Likewise, the ineffectiveness of criminal justice systems and related institutions in combating slavery and human trafficking has also resulted in very few successful prosecutions and conviction of traffickers.

That is why, very serious actions have to be done in the future. Indeed, to be effective, national, continental and universal strategies for combating this phenomenon must adopt a multi-disciplinary approach incorporating prevention, protection of Human rights of victims and prosecution of traffickers. It is also important to have a harmony between the relevant national laws and ensure that these laws are applied uniformly and effectively. It is evident that the criminal responsibility should not only be that of recruiters and intermediaries, but also the users of exploited persons should be criminalised.

Moreover, both trafficking inside national borders and global trafficking have to be taken seriously. Actually, trafficking nearly always involves several states and in order to address the issue effectively, there is need of successful International cooperation among countries of origin, of transit and of destination. This is fundamental for slavery and human trafficking to be eliminated. In this regard, promoting International cooperation and cooperation's mechanisms is one of the most important things to do, in order to combat traffickers. This emphasises international assistance and cooperation between states in criminal matters.

Finally, legal measures to combat trafficking will fail without

mechanisms to implement and monitor these laws. Consequently, it is urgent that this crime is properly prosecuted and that preventive measures are taken to stop it from spreading. In this regard, more actions should be done as to firmly condemn the violations of human rights committed against human beings who are sold as slaves. All states have to share their financial resources to facilitate the evacuation of migrants who are regularly trapped in detention Centers, and bring them the assistance and the necessary humanitarian aid. It is required to launch full international investigation into these acts.

Also, the UN Security Council is invited to assume its responsibilities in the preservation of peace and security in the world. The International community has to strengthen its efforts to combat human trafficking and smuggling of migrants through the implementation of the provisions of the UN Convention on Transnational Organised Crime and its supplementing Protocols against Trafficking in Persons and Smuggling of Migrants by improving both national and International legislation.

Not all these actions can be efficient without the support of the Mass Media and the civil society. More actions have to be done, in order to denounce these crimes and support the victims by allowing them to express themselves and to tell the stories about their horror, without fear, promote creative and innovative

solutions to human trafficking and address trauma, poverty, and inequality.

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